

Board Characteristics and Financial Performance of Deposits Money Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

Corporate error and managerial concerns stakeholders have expressed worry about the state of the banking industry, therefore the study looked into how board characteristics affected the deposit money banks in Nigeria's financial performance. The study's data were collected from the sampled companies' annual reports and accounts for the years 2018 through 2022. Board meetings, size, and independence serve as proxies for board characteristics. With ROA, financial performance was proxied. The study's conclusions showed that board meetings and independent contractors have a small but favourable effect on ROA. Whereas board size has a negligible and adverse effect on ROA. The study recommended that in order to increase the ROA of the sampled banks, board meetings and board independence should be sufficiently maintained. In order to increase the ROA, size should be kept low.

Keywords: Financial performance, Board characteristics, Board independent, Board meeting, Return on asset

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1.0 Introduction

The majority of contemporary organizations may view enhancing their financial performance as their top priority. Financial performance acts as a gauge of the organization's financial health since it shows how successfully a company organizes its skills and resources to produce revenues in order to achieve desired profits (Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018; Abubakar, Onipe, & Nma, 2021). It assesses a company's overall financial health over a specific time period and is used to compare businesses in the same industry or to aggregate industries or sectors (Adamu & Saleh, 2020). It aggregates the performance of many industries or business sectors or analyzes the performance of comparable businesses

operating in the same industry. Performance is used to assess a company's financial health over a certain time frame.

Board characteristics are all company's board's qualities and characteristics that enable the effective and successful pursuit of or realization of all of the interests of the numerous stakeholders (Augustine & Juliet, 2022). The characteristics may be quantitative or intangible; the quantitative variables include board size, independence, shareholdings, meeting frequency, gender diversity, and board membership competence; the qualitative or intangible variables include the generation of positive values and quality decisions (Oyedokun, 2019; Kamaludin, Ibrahim, & Sundarassen, 2020). The size of the board has an impact on investment levels and financial performance. Independent decision-making by the board may result in better choices that are best for the business, and good choices help to improve financial performance. board dimensions.

According to agency theory, the board must disclose all governance-related matters in order to determine whether its objectives are aligned with those of its shareholders. This is due to the fact that executive directors are more knowledgeable than shareholders about a company's ongoing operations and true value at any given time (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020). As a result, management could take advantage of this information asymmetry to their advantage by avoiding risky investments (which tend to be more profitable) to protect their position and job and the kinds of investments that ultimately have an impact on the financial performance of the company. Managers typically focus on increasing sales rather than profit because their compensation is dependent on revenue earned rather than profit (Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019).

Accordingly, this study's goal is to evaluate how board characteristics affect the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria by taking into account the moderating function of co-gender. Thus, the following are the study's hypotheses:

H₀₁: Board size has no significant effect on financial performance of listed Deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Board independent has no significant effect on financial performance of listed Deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Board meeting frequency has no significant effect on financial performance of Listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review

Ahmed and Kehinde (2022) looked into the connections between board meetings, company size, and financial performance of 13 Nigerian listed industrial goods companies between 2012 and 2021. The financial performance, as determined by return on assets (ROA), was the dependent variable. The independent variables included board meetings and board size, while the control variables included firm age and size. The Nigerian Stock Exchange website is where the data were gathered. The methods employed were correlation, random-effects GLS regression, and descriptive statistics. Stata was the tool utilized. The study's conclusions demonstrated that the board meetings' financial performance was unfavorable and negligible. Yet, a considerable beneficial impact on financial performance was found in relation to board size.

In addition, Monther, Mustafa, and Ainulashikin (2022) looked into the moderating role that Shariah Committee Quality (SCQ) has on the association between the success of Malaysian companies and their board of directors' effectiveness between 2010 and 2017. Return on Equity and Return on Assets were used as Dependent Variables in the study. Independent Variables included Board Size, Board Independence, Muslim Directors, Gender Diversity, Control Variables: Firm Size, Firm Age, and Leverage Ratio, and Moderating Variable: Shariah Committee. Eleven Takaful businesses that are licensed by Malaysia's central bank, Bank Negara Malaysia [BNM], produced secondary data. The data was analyzed using Stata, panel regression, and regression analysis. The results indicated a positive correlation between performance and BDE.

Further, using data from 56 nations between 2010 and 2019, Achraf and Mohamed (2022) accurately identified the strengths and shortcomings of the Shariah Advisory Board (SAB), which can assist Islamic Banks (IBs) in optimizing their Financial Performance (FP). In the study, the following variables were used as dependent variables: liquidity, profitability, and efficiency; independent variables included SAB size; control variables included bank age, bank type, and bank size; mastery of Shariah principles by SAB members; and scientific competence of SAB members. The study employed correlation, regression, and descriptive statistics as methods. The conclusions showed that the size, frequency of meetings, and presence of Shariah experts on the Shariah Advisory Board enhanced the Islamic banks' financial performance.

In another study, Augustine and Juliet (2022) investigated how corporate board characteristics affected Nigerian conglomerates' financial results between 2011 and 2020. The variables employed in the study were as follows: The dependent variable was return on assets, while the independent variables were board size, independence, committees, meetings, and shareholdings. Regression analysis (random effect model) was employed as a data analysis approach on secondary data. Results showed that the size, independence, and equity holdings of the audit committee and board had a significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian conglomerates. Board meetings, however, did not appear to have a substantial impact on the financial results of Nigerian conglomerates. It is necessary to investigate alternative industries.

However, Ayman (2022) looked into how the qualities of the audit committee affected Saudi non-financial companies' financial performance between 2010 and 2019. Return on assets (ROA) was used as a dependent variable, whereas ownership, leverage, firm size, board independence, and meetings and size of the audit committee were used as control variables. The audit committee also had financial knowledge and independence. For data analysis, the study used panel data and secondary data approaches (pooled OLS, fixed, and random effects). According to the study, there is a significant and positive correlation between financial success and the independence and financial expertise of the audit committee.

Also, In their 2022 study, Hariem and Turgut investigated the impact of Corporate Governance (GC) on the outcomes of non-financial companies that were listed between 2002 and 2018 on the German Frankfurt Stock Exchange. Return on equity and return on assets were used as dependent variables; independent variables included the CEO duality, the audit committee, the board of directors, and financial leverage; a dummy variable was the implementation of IFRS in 2005. The German Frankfurt Stock Exchange provided secondary data. The research employed the following methodologies: regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation matrix and VIF. Findings showed that while CEO duality has no statistically significant impact on company financial performance, the audit committee and board of directors' features do have a substantial and detrimental impact.

In another study, Hussein and Ahmed (2022) looked at how BOD share ownership affected BOD remuneration, how BOD share ownership affected company performance, and how BOD share ownership and compensation interacted to affect firm performance in Saudi Arabia from 2005 to 2019. The following factors were utilized in the study: ROE was the

dependent variable, and firm size was the control variable. The independent variables were board independence, size, share ownership, and remuneration. We made use of secondary sources. The following methods were employed in the study: pooled ordinary least squares (POLS), descriptive statistics, and correlation. According to the research, higher compensation for the Board of Directors results in better corporate performance. It also suggests that the interaction between the effect of compensation and BOD share-ownership on firm performance is beneficial.

In the same vein, Mohammed, Ridzwaana, Jalali, and Fakarudin (2022) looked into how board characteristics and corporate sustainability disclosure compliance (CSDC) were related, and how financial success might have a moderating effect. The research that was employed was Nigeria's Corporate Sustainability Disclosure Compliance (LCSDC) from 2011 to 2017. The audit committee, board independence, board size, and gender diversity were all employed as independent variables in the study. Firm size and age are control variables, whereas ROA and ROE are moderating variables. The study used secondary data, which was gathered from 118 companies that are listed in Nigeria. The dynamic GMM regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation are the techniques used. The study found that there is a strong positive interaction between board size, board independence, gender diversity, and audit committee and the effects of company and board qualities on CSDC. This suggests that return on equity and return on assets have a moderating effect.

Also, Sonia, Zied, and Abdelwahed (2022) investigated the potential impact of corporate social practices (CSP) on the relationship between board gender diversity and financial performance in France between 2005 and 2019. The research used Secondary information derived from 120 French companies included in the SBF index. The following variables were employed in the study: size of the board, specific talents, cultural diversity, female employees, intensity of R&D, separation between the CEO and the chairman, lag in the dependent variable, and measure and leverage of the independent variables. According to a mediation effect steps analysis, gender diversity on the board has a greater effect on CSI than CSR. The findings validated that CSP had a disproportionate impact on CSI's financial results. According to the study, CSI functions as a mediator between financial performance and gender diversity on the board.

The research mentioned above makes clear that there is inconclusive empirical data about the relationship between board size and a company's financial performance. Studies by

(Abubakar et al., 2021; Achraf & Mohamed, 2022; Ahmad, Yusuf, Ahmad, & Nazrul, 2017; Ali, Nejia, & Abdelfettah, 2018; Anissa, 2021; Augustine & Juliet, 2022; Mohammed, Ridzwana, Jalila, & Fakarudin, 2022; Monther et al., 2022; Muhammad, Sun, & Ramiz, 2017; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024) provide witness to this. found a favorable correlation between financial performance and board size. However, research by Ibrahim, Okika, Yunusa, and Janada (2020); Elamer and Benyazid (2018); and Ahmed and Kehinde (2022) revealed a negative correlation between board size and financial performance. Additionally, research by Monther et al. (2022), Ayman (2022), Augustine and Juliet (2022), and Abubakar et al. (2021) revealed a positive correlation between board independence and financial performance. Additionally, a study by Achraf and Mohamed (2022) found a favourable correlation between the frequency of board meetings and financial performance. However, studies by Augustine & Juliet (2022), Ahmed and Kehinde (2022), and Abubakar et al. (2021) found a negative correlation between the frequency of board meetings and financial performance.

3.0 Methodology

A correlational research design was used for this investigation. The research makes use of secondary data that was taken from the annual reports of each of the fourteen (14) listed deposit money banks in the Nigerian Exchange Group, covering the years 2018 to 2022. The study used a sample of the entire population. Multiple regression analysis and descriptive statistics are data analysis approaches. The variables of the study, together with their measurement, kind, and source, are shown in Table 1. The study's model was taken from research projects by Mohammed et al. and Harriem and Turgut (2022).

Table 1: Variable Measurement

VARIABLES	MEASUREMENT	TYPE	SOURCE
RETURN ON ASSET	PAT/TOTAL ASSET	DEPENDENT	Paolo, Virginia, & Javier (2021)
BOARD SIZE	NO. OF DIRECTORS	INDEPENDENT	Hussein & Ahmed, (2022)
MEETING	NO. OF MEETINGS IN A FINANCIAL YEAR	INDEPENDENT	Augustine & Juliet (2020)
INDEPENDENCE	NED/TOTAL DIRECTORS	INDEPENDENT	Mohammed, Ridzwaana, Jalali & Fakarudin

(2022)

CO-GENDER	MALE:FEMALE	CONTROL	Muhammad, Abdullah, Merve & Ali, (2020)
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Source: Generated by the researcher

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SIZE_{it} + \beta_2 BIND_{it} + \beta_4 MTNG_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where: α = the constant

β = the coefficient

e_{it} = Random error term where i is cross sectional and t time identifier

ROA = Return on asset

SIZE = Board size

BIND = Board Independence

MTNG = Meetings

ϵ = Error term

4. 0 Results and Discussion

This section discussed the descriptive, correlation and regressions analysis as contained and discussed below:

TABLE 2 Descriptive statistics

	SIZE	INDEFENDENT	MEETINGS	GENDER	ROA
Mean	13.400	0.649	6.314	0.400	0.020
Standard Error	0.384	0.017	0.353	0.016	0.003
Median	14.000	0.600	6.000	0.419	0.013
Standard Deviation	3.210	0.145	2.952	0.137	0.024
Sample Variance	10.301	0.021	8.711	0.019	0.001
Kurtosis	-0.242	-0.667	2.059	0.690	13.806
Skewness	0.284	0.385	0.915	-0.389	3.421
Minimum	7.000	0.333	0.000	0.010	0.003
Maximum	21.000	0.929	16.000	0.711	0.149
Count	70	70	70	70	70

Source: Generated from the data collected from annual reports and accounts of the sampled banks

Table 2 showed 70 observations of fourteen listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The mean ROA 0.02 implies that the sampled banks have an average of 2%. The min, max and standard deviation of ROA was 0.00, 0.149 and 0,024 respectively implies that the sampled banks have minimum of 0% ROA and a maximum of 14.9%. The standard deviation of 0.024 higher than a mean implies a higher variation in ROA among the sampled banks.

Size has a mean 13.4 implying the sampled companies has average of 13 members. The minimum is 7 and maximum of 21 board size. The standard deviation is 3 which is lower than a mean implies low variation of board size of the sampled banks. The mean meeting is 6 meaning the sampled banks have an average of 6 meetings in a year with a minimum of 0 and maximum of 16 meetings in a year.

The mean, min, max and standard deviation of independent are 0.649, 0.333, 0.929 and 0.145. also, the mean, min, max and standard deviation of gender are 0.4, 0.01, 0.7 and 0.14.

Correlation Matrix

Table present correlation matrix of the dependent and independent variables as contain in the table below:

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	SIZE	INDEFENDENT	MEETINGS	GENDER	ROA
SIZE	1				
INDEFENDENT	-0.136	1			
MEETINGS	0.198	-0.168	1		
GENDER	0.710	-0.111	0.242	1	
ROA	0.004	0.096	-0.070	-0.022	1

Source: Generated from data collected from annual report and accounts of sampled banks

Table 3 shows the correlation coefficients on the relationship between the dependent variable (ROA), independent variables (Size, Independent, Meetings and Gender) The values of the correlation coefficient range from -1 to 1. The sign of the correlation coefficient indicates the direction of the relationship (positive or negative), the absolute values of the correlation coefficient indicate the strength, with larger values indicating stronger relationships. The correlation coefficients on the main diagonal are 1.0, because each variable has a perfect positive linear relationship with itself.

Regression analysis

Table 4: Regression Result

	Coef.	Robust		
		Err.	T	P>t
ROA				
MEETINGS	0.000	0.001	-0.730	0.469
GENDER	0.177	0.129	1.370	0.175
INDEFENDENT	0.110	0.087	1.250	0.215
SIZE	-0.001	0.001	-0.480	0.630
_cons	-0.044	0.046	-0.950	0.347

Table 4 reveals meetings has coefficient (0.000) and prob. F (0.469) which means positive and insignificant effect. This implies that an increase in meeting other variables remain constant will increase ROA positively but insignificantly. This could mean that some spending are made during each meetings.

Table 4 reveals gender has coefficient (0.177) and prob. F (0.175) which means positive and insignificant effect. This implies that variation in gender has positively but insignificantly. Similarly, board independent has positive and insignificant impact on ROA. Board size has negative and insignificant impact on ROA. This implies an increase in size other variables remain constant, will reduce the ROA insignificantly.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, it was determined that among the tested banks, board meetings, board gender, and board independence had a favourable but little impact. The sampled banks have had a negative and negligible influence from board size. The study suggested that in order to increase the ROA of the tested banks, board meetings, board gender, and board independence should be sufficiently maintained. In order to increase the ROA, size should be kept low.

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